

WHO
Strategic Advisory Group
on Malaria Eradication

Working papers

Group 2: Lessons learned from previous eradication efforts

Title

Lessons learned from the dracunculiasis (Guinea worm disease) eradication programme

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This working paper was commissioned by the WHO Strategic Advisory Group on Malaria Eradication between 2016 and 2019.

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Lessons Learned from the Dracunculiasis (Guinea worm disease) Eradication Programme

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I conducted a review of the dracunculiasis (Guinea worm disease) eradication programme to identify elements related to governance and coordination, research and development, innovations, funding, political and community mobilization, health systems and surveillance to find lessons that would be applicable to malaria elimination. I conducted a literature search in PubMed using the keywords [(dracunculiasis OR 'Guinea' worm) AND (elimination OR eradication)] in the title or abstract and identified 267 publications. I reviewed all abstracts to determine whether they would provide relevant information and reviewed the full content of 48 publications, of which 41 were included in this review (although not all publications are cited if they provided similar information to another paper).

Dracunculiasis, a self-limiting parasitic (*Dracunculus medinensis*) infection transmitted exclusively by water through the oral route alone, was first proposed for eradication as a potential indicator of the achievement of the goals of the International Drinking Water Supply and Sanitation Decade (IDWSSD, 1981-1990).(1) The adoption in 1986 of WHA resolution 39.21 acknowledged the special opportunity afforded by the IDWSSD for combating dracunculiasis.(2) A WHA resolution in 1991, when there were approximately 400,000 reported cases globally, called for eradication by 1995, but it was not achieved. The date for global eradication has been postponed several times: in 2004, the ministers of health at the WHA resolved to eradicate dracunculiasis by 2009. When that date was not met, the global initiative determined to interrupt transmission as soon as possible but without a defined target date.(3) The last mile of dracunculiasis eradication is proving to be more challenging than anticipated: there were more new human cases of dracunculiasis in the first half of 2019 (n=19) than the same period in 2018 (n=5).(4) Additionally, the identification of dogs in the transmission cycle in some countries poses an existential threat to dracunculiasis eradication.(5)

Global leadership for dracunculiasis eradication has largely come from outside WHO, initially from the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) that was designated the WHO Collaborating Centre for Research, Training and Eradication of Dracunculiasis in 1984, and given responsibility for monitoring progress towards eradication and for providing technical assistance to countries.(6) The US CDC began close collaboration with The Carter Center in 1986.

The Carter Center provided direct technical assistance to countries eliminating dracunculiasis, placing international staff at subnational level to assist with institutional capacity building and to provide extra support for implementation and monitoring of interventions. WHO played a role in surveillance in areas free from disease and in countries at the pre-certification stage.(7) The receipt of a \$28.5 million grant from the BMGF in 2000 clarified roles and responsibilities, with The Carter Center responsible for countries reporting >100 cases per year, WHO for countries with <100 cases per year as well as for pre-certification and certification, and UNICEF to assist selected countries with funds from other sources to provide safe drinking water.(8)

From the beginning, funding was an issue for the dracunculiasis eradication effort. WHO lacked sufficient resources to perform the surveillance and coordination function it was mandated to do, and other agencies similarly faced funding challenges. In 2008, The Carter Center and WHO made a joint approach to the BMGF and the United Kingdom's Department for International Development, which led to financial pledges from both.(7)

In 1987, an Interagency Coordinating Group for Dracunculiasis Eradication began holding quarterly or semi-annual meetings.(6) These meetings were seen as critical to ensuring coordination between partners and maintaining momentum towards eradication. National programmes also hold their own annual review meetings, often attended by members of partner organizations.

The eradication of dracunculiasis was originally conceived as a sub-goal and indicator of the success of the WHO's IDWSSD. When it became clear that provision of safe water was unlikely to happen quickly enough to achieve eradication of dracunculiasis, there was a shift in the programme towards behavior change and use of filtering technologies to reduce infection.

Initially in many countries, the dracunculiasis eradication campaign became viable when the first national active disease surveillance effort got underway and helped to document the extent of disease transmission in the country.(9) Political will for eradication was achieved in part through the personal, high-level contacts of former US President Jimmy Carter, who had been convinced to lead the eradication campaign through his Center. President Carter convinced the heads of state of Nigeria, Mali, Uganda and Ghana to lead their countries to eliminate dracunculiasis, and then helped negotiate a 4-month cease fire during the Sudan civil war in 1995 that breathed life back into the dracunculiasis elimination efforts in Sudan that had been stalled by civil strife.

A common aspect to most national dracunculiasis elimination programmes was the integration of the programme within, or in close collaboration with, the healthcare system. While the national level provided overall strategic guidance along with monitoring and

evaluation, the interventions were implemented through the primary healthcare system. This did not always result in optimal implementation, (2) and was not always seen as favorable to eradication. Donald R. Hopkins of The Carter Center noted that healthcare systems were designed to control, not eradicate diseases, and would be unlikely to create the sense of urgency that elimination programmes required.(10)

The first priority of dracunculiasis eradication programmes was to establish active surveillance across the country using networks of village health workers to conduct surveillance and health education.(11) Passive surveillance for dracunculiasis was inadequate at the onset of the eradication campaign, detecting less than 3% of all cases and initially most countries did not know the distribution of the disease at the central level.(11) At times when active surveillance systems for dracunculiasis could not be sustained, the programme suffered setbacks.(7)

The approach to dracunculiasis eradication also evolved over time but without a directed research agenda. The main intervention at the beginning of the eradication effort was provision of clean water, but when that proved too challenging in many contexts, the use of cloth water filters was evaluated and then introduced, followed by nylon water filters that were found to be more effective, and eventually filter straws.(12) In more recent years, the use of case containment during worm emergence and protection of water sources has proven effective.(13)

Although occasional *Dracunculus medinensis* (the causative agent of dracunculiasis) infections in dogs had been reported as early as the 1950s, reappearance of the disease in Chad in 2010, 10 years after the last case had been reported, was caused by infections in dogs that were serving as a reservoir for human infections.(5, 14, 15) Investigators are now examining the possibility that intermediate hosts such as fish and frogs may also play a role and transmission, and new control efforts are targeting infections in dogs in hopes that eradication can still be achieved.(3)

References

1. Bourne P. Global eradication of guinea worm. *J R Soc Med.* 1982;75:1-3. accessed
2. Biswas G, Sankara D, Agua-Agum J, Maiga A. Dracunculiasis (guinea worm disease): Eradication without a drug or a vaccine. *Phil Trans R Soc B.* 2013;368. accessed
3. Hopkins D, Ruiz-Tiben E, Eberhard M, Weiss A, Withers Jr P, Roy S et al. Dracunculiasis eradication: Are we there yet? *Am J Trop Med Hyg.* 2018;99:388-95. accessed
4. WHO. Monthly report on dracunculiasis cases, january-june 2019. *Wkly Epidem Rec.* 2019;94:378-9. accessed
5. Eberhard ML, Ruiz-Tiben E, Hopkins DR, Farrell C, Toe F, Weiss A et al. The peculiar epidemiology of dracunculiasis in chad. *Am J Trop Med Hyg.* 2014;90:61–70. accessed
6. Ruiz-Tiben E, Hopkins D. Dracunculiasis (guinea worm disease) eradication. *Adv Parasit.* 2006;61:276-309. accessed
7. Cairncross S, Tayeh A, Korkor A. Why is dracunculiasis eradication taking so long? . *Trends in Parasitology.* 2012;28:225-30. accessed
8. Hopkins DR, Ruiz-Tiben E, Diallo N, Withers PC, Jr., Maguire JH. Dracunculiasis eradication: And now, sudan. *Am J Trop Med Hyg.* 2002;67:415-22. accessed
9. Edungbola LD, Withers PC, Jr., Braide EI, Kale OO, Sadiq LO, Nwobi BC et al. Mobilization strategy for guinea worm eradication in nigeria. *Am J Trop Med Hyg.* 1992;47:529-38. accessed
10. Hopkins DR. Perspectives from the dracunculiasis eradication programme. *Bull World Health Organ.* 1998;76 Suppl 2:38-41. accessed
11. Muller R. Guinea worm disease - the final chapter? *Trends in Parasitology.* 2005;21:521-4. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pt.2005.08.024>.
12. Richard F, Ruiz-Tiben E, Hopkins D. Dracunculiasis eradication and the legacy of the smallpox campaign: What's new and innovative? What's old and principled? *Vaccine.* 2011;29S:D86-D90. accessed
13. Hochberg N, Ruiz-Tiben E, Downs P, Fagan J, Maguire J. The role of case containment centers in the eradication of dracunculiasis in togo and ghana. *Am J Trop Med Hyg.* 2008;79:722-7. accessed
14. Muhammad G, Khan MZ, Athar M, Saqib M. Dracunculus infection in a dog during the 'post-eradication' period: The need for a longer period of surveillance. *Ann Trop Med Parasitol.* 2005;99:105-7. doi: 10.1179/136485905X19847.
15. Sankaranarayanan M, Ramamirtham S, Lakshminarayanan KS. Record of the guinea worm-dracunculus medinensis in an alsatian bitch. *Indian Vet J.* 1965;42:972-3. accessed